

Formal account of ghost snapshots in a verification tool for RUST

Internship report – MPRI M2

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General context

What is the report about ? Where does the problem come from ? What is the state of the art in that area ?

CREUSOT [Denis et al. (2022)] is a realistic deductive verifier, inspired by RUSTHORN [Matsushita et al. (2021)], to efficiently encode RUST programs and offload proof obligations using SMT solvers, thanks to the WHY3 framework [Bobot et al. (2011)].

To demonstrate the soundness of CREUSOT, RUSTHORNBELT [Matsushita et al. (2022)] has been developed, which is an extension of the RUSTBELT formal model [Jung et al. (2017)], incorporating RUSTHORN features, notably functional correctness.

Over time, CREUSOT has implemented extensions to enhance the user experience, moving away from the original proven model. Some unsound interactions have been discovered [Xavier et al. (To be published)], and some restrictions have been proposed, but not yet formalised.

These restrictions have been implemented in CREUSOT, and are expressive enough to prove CREUSOT's extensive test suite. However, this implementation does not constitute a formal proof and could lead to other unsoundness when dealing with deeper interactions (e.g. `unsafe` RUST code).

Research problem

What specific question(s) have you studied ? What motivates the question ? What are its applications/consequences ? Is it a new problem ? Why did you choose this problem ?

The main problem studied is the interaction between snapshots (a type of ghost code) and mutable borrows, which can result in unsoundness. Specifically, a causality loop occurs whereby the expected final value of a borrow depends on itself. The key issue is that without proper restrictions, the unsoundness reappears.

To validate the restriction proposal, deep modifications to RUSTHORNBELT's model are required. This necessitates knowledge of both the separation logic framework IRIS [Jung et al. (2018)] and RUSTBELT, which I had the opportunity to work with extensively during my previous internships.

Your contribution

What is your answer to the research problem ? Please remain at a high level ; technical details should be given in the main body of the report. Pay special attention to the description of the scientific approach

We successfully proved that the restriction proposal is sound and expressive enough to prove each case that the initial model could solve. We also simplified the model, revealing that misunderstood complex interactions in RUSTHORNBELT were necessary to avoid the same kind of unsound interactions encountered by CREUSOT.

These modifications have required changes to how *prophecies* are (1) represented, from a value to a unique identifier making borrows *non-extensional*, and (2) accessed, from unrestricted access to being accessible only at a specification level. A new operation has also been introduced to deal with the new representation of prophecies, retrieving values from identifiers.

We also introduced the notion of snapshots directly into the model, which was straightforward thanks to our modifications. We provided a case study on `std::cell::Cell<T>` that relies on `unsafe` code, written in both RUSTHORNBELT and CREUSOT. In the former case, we proved the interface and the example, whereas in the latter case, we axiomatised the interface thanks to the model, and successfully proved the same example using the axiomatisation.

Arguments supporting its validity

What is the evidence that your solution is a good solution ? (Experiments ? Proofs ?)

Comment on the robustness of your solution : does it rely on assumptions, and if so, to what extent ?

Our formalised solution aligns with the proposed restrictions while maintaining the same level of expressivity. Furthermore, a foundational model is still required for validating modification proposals and for demonstrating axiomatised interfaces, such as the example with `std::cell::Cell<T>`.

This solution has been developed using the ROCQ proof assistant, which provides a high degree of assurance. It is based on state-of-the-art research projects that are well known within the community. Furthermore, our modifications did not modified the adequacy proof.

Summary and future work

What did you contribute to the area ? What comes next ? What is a good next step or question ?

This work was a necessary step towards building strong confidence in the CREUSOT tool. Up to our knowledge, this work is the first to model and validate the proposed restrictions. It also demonstrates that RUSTHORNBELT can be used to investigate further extensions in CREUSOT.

A next step would be to add support for *type invariants* to the model. This also required non-trivial changes to CREUSOT, such as introducing the concept of *prophetic invariants*.

Furthermore, the language behind RUSTBELT and RUSTHORNBELT, λ_{Rust} , is a simplified version of RUST that does not take into account the notion of *places*, which is important for the correctness of an analysis called *final borrows*. This work could take inspiration from the related foundational work REFINEDRUST [Gäher et al. (2024)].

Another question would be to merge both RUSTHORNBELT, which features functional correctness, and RELAXEDRUSTBELT [Dang et al. (2019)], which features *relaxed memory*, in order to investigate how to reason in CREUSOT under a relaxed memory setting.

I would like to thank the members of the TOCCATA group for their warm welcome. Many thanks for the constructive and varied discussions during the breaks.

Special thanks to JACQUES-HENRI JOURDAN for trusting me with this internship and for his help throughout the implementation and the writing of this internship report.

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Rocq mechanisation

The RUSTHORNBELT project is fully mechanised in ROCQ. The implementation can be found at the following link: <https://gitlab.mpi-sws.org/iris/lambda-rust/-/tree/masters/rusthornbelt/>.

ROCQ code was written during the internship, which can be found in the [lafeychine/proph-update](#) branch.

1. Introduction

Programming languages provide varying levels of abstraction for memory management. Languages without abstraction, like C or C++, require developers to follow a strict set of rules to prevent memory-related errors such as out-of-bounds access, use-after-free, or memory leaks. Conversely, languages with higher levels of abstraction, like Haskell or Scala, do not require such strict discipline due to the inclusion of runtime features such as garbage collection. However, these features may not be compatible with certain use cases, such as systems programming, where fine-grained control over memory is mandatory.

Recently, the RUST programming language [Matsakis & Klock (2014)] has filled this gap with its unique type system along finely-tuned compile-time tracking, offering a tradeoff between low-level control and high-level safety. RUST has been widely adopted in major critical projects, notably the Linux Kernel [Torvalds (2022)], due to its ability to create highly reliable system programs.

RUST ensures memory safety at compile time through the fundamental principle of “Aliasing xor Mutation”. This means that a borrowed variable must be either in a mutable but uniquely owned state (written `&mut`) or in an aliased but immutable state (written `&`). This principle eliminates a wide range of common low-level programming errors, particularly in concurrent contexts such as iterator invalidation. An analysis in the RUST compiler, called *borrow checker*, is responsible for verifying that this principle is respected.

```
1 let mut x: i32 = 0;
2 let bor_x: &mut i32 = &mut x;
// x = 2; * Forbidden: x is frozen while the lifetime of x is active *
3 *bor_x = 1;
4 assert!(x == 1);
```

Lifetime of x

Figure 1: Example of mutably borrowing variables in RUST

This program begins by defining an integer variable `x`, of type `i32`, with the value `0`. Then, the instruction `&mut x` allows the variable `bor_x` to mutably borrow `x`, and obtain the type `&mut i32`.

When a variable is borrowed, RUST automatically generates a lifetime tied to that variable (here, `bor_x`) and *freezes* the borrowed value (here, `x`), thereby preventing any other access (here, `x = 2` in line 3).

The program then writes the value `1` to `x` through the borrow `bor_x`. From this program point onwards, the variable `bor_x` will no longer be used, thus ending its lifetime and *unfreezing* the borrowed value. The program can therefore access to `x` again, and finally asserts that its value is equals to `1`.

Despite verifying that programs do not have memory-related errors, RUST’s type system does not provide any guarantee about runtime failure. Indeed, the above example compiles but it might throw an exception at runtime if one asks a false assertion (e.g. `assert!(x == 2)`).

Thanks to its promises on memory safety, there has been significant research on building verification tools capable of establishing functional correctness properties of RUST programs.

Firstly, RUSTHORN [Matsushita et al. (2021)] presents an approach to reasoning about a well-typed RUST program (e.g., verifying its functional correctness) as if it were a purely functional program, eliminating the need for explicit heap modelling. Notably, this approach involves representing mutable borrows using *prophecies*, which are logical placeholders for the final value of mutably borrowed objects.

Secondly, RUSTHORNBELT [Matsushita et al. (2022)] extends RUSTHORN with a semantic formal foundation. It provides a type system that interprets RUST types as logical predicates describing their behaviour. The type

system also handles prophecies, allowing the logical model to track the evolution of mutable state throughout program execution.

Thirdly, CREUSOT [Denis et al. (2022)] is a deductive verification framework, that translates RUST programs into logical specifications that can be discharged to SMT solvers, thanks to WHY3 [Bobot et al. (2011)]. It is based on both RUSTHORN's encoding and RUSTHORNBELT's model. CREUSOT is a tool designed for RUST developers who want to prove functional correctness of realistic RUST codebases, and features relevant mechanisms to this purpose. One of these is the concept of snapshots, which captures the logical state of a value at a specific program point and can be used later.

However, [Xavier et al. (To be published)] demonstrated how a causality loop could be created using snapshots, whereby the final value of the borrow is defined in terms of itself. To solve this issue, a modification for CREUSOT has been proposed so that the logical representation of a mutable borrow becomes *non-extensional*. Despite this constraint, CREUSOT preserves the expressive power required for most verification tasks.

This interaction was possible despite the fact that the CREUSOT's underlying model, RUSTHORNBELT, has been formalised is because the model has not implemented snapshots. Our work extends the RUSTHORNBELT model to include snapshots, using the proposed representation of mutable borrows and proving them sound.

Implementing this restriction has necessitated fundamental changes to the model, while preserving its expressiveness by verifying cases that do not respect the RUST's fundamental principle. Notably, this work has changed how prophecies are represented, making borrows non-extensional, and accessed, ensuring prophecies are only accessible at a specification level.

This report first introduces CREUSOT and the discovered unsoundness interaction (Section 2), then describes the RUSTHORNBELT's type system and the attempt to introduce snapshots (Section 3). This is followed by a description of how the type system has been modified following the proposed solution (Section 4), before concluding with a presentation of the semantic model to prove the validity of the type system (Section 5).

2. The CREUSOT deductive verification tool

This section explains how RUST programs are encoded using RUSTHORN's representation (Section 2.1), followed by an explanation of specific feature introduced in CREUSOT (Section 2.2) and how those two features combined leads to an unsoundness (Section 2.3).

2.1. Representation of RUST programs

When it comes to automatic verification, it is preferable to prove programs represented as pure functions that have no side effects. Indeed, the strength of the solver is directly linked to the complexity of the model.

In RUST, an object can be in one of three states: fully-owned (τ), shared ($\&\tau$), or mutably borrowed ($\&\text{mut } \tau$). In the fully-owned state, any modification can be described in a standard state-passing style. In the shared state, no modification can arise. However, mutable borrows need to be encoded as functional values.

Thanks to the RUST's fundamental principle, a value that has been mutably borrowed cannot be directly accessed as it is considered *frozen*, the ownership is transferred to the borrower until the borrow ends. During this time, the value can only be accessed and modified through the borrower.

From a logic point of view, there is a close relationship between the lender and the borrower: the value is modified by the borrower, but must be transferred back to the lender when the borrow ends.

RUSTHORN [Matsushita et al. (2021)] showed that any well-typed RUST program can be translated into a first-order logic specification without any stateful memory representation, allowing one to prove functional correctness efficiently using SMT solvers.

To achieve this, RUSTHORN uses a prophecy-based encoding that links the original owner of the value to the various mutations it has undergone. This encoding is a tuple of the *current value* being modified throughout the execution, and the *final value* being the value when the borrow ends.

For example, let's show the physical and logical representations of variables in the program shown in Figure 1:

	<code>// Physical view:</code>	<code>Logical view:</code>
<code>1 let mut x: i32 = 0;</code>	<code>// x → 0</code>	<code>x ↦ 0</code>
<code>2 let bor_x: &mut i32 = &mut x;</code>	<code>// x → 0, bor_x → &x</code>	<code>x ↦ α, bor_x ↦ (0, α)</code>
<code>3 *bor_x = 1;</code>	<code>// x → 1, bor_x → &x</code>	<code>x ↦ α, bor_x ↦ (1, α)</code>
	<code>//</code>	<code>* α = 1, by resolving bor_x *</code>
<code>4 assert!(x == 1);</code>		

Figure 2: Creation and resolution of mutable borrows, showing physical view (\rightarrow) and logical view (\mapsto).

The leftmost commented column shows the physical view, in which any access involving `bor_x` results in dereferencing `x`. By contrast, the rightmost commented column shows the logical view of the memory used by CREUSOT, using RUSTHORN's encoding.

According to the encoding, the final value of a borrow needs to be *propheied*: a new logical value, referred to as a *prophecy*, is created. This *prophecy* replaces the variable's value (here, $x \mapsto \alpha$), and the borrower is represented by the current variable's value and the created *prophecy* (here, $bor_x \mapsto (0, \alpha)$).

Any modifications made through the borrow will be kept by the *current value* tuple field, which can be modified using the state-passing style (here, $bor_x \mapsto (1, \alpha)$). It is worth noting that, even though the underlying value is being modified, it will not yet be propagated to the lender thanks to the *prophecy*.

When the borrower's lifetime ends, the *current value* field can no longer be modified. The *current value* and *final value* fields become equal, hence *resolving* the *prophecy* (here, $\alpha = 1$). The assertion can now be successfully satisfied, as the value of `x` is indeed equals to 1. This mechanism, called *resolution*, is not written in the RUST code itself, but is instead generated for verification purposes based on RUSTHORN's method.

As a side note, the resolution does not actually occur at the end of the borrower's lifetime. Instead, it occurs between the borrower's last use and the end of its lifetime. This fact will become explicit with the typing rules described in Section 3.2.3.

This first example illustrates the key mechanism of *prophecies*, which can be applied to address all cases of borrows in RUST programs while ensuring efficient offloading to SMT solvers.

2.2. Snapshot mechanism

Over time, CREUSOT introduced multiple features on top of RUSTHORN to enhance the user experience. One such feature to help verification of the program are *snapshots*, which takes a snapshot of the memory by capturing its environment. As this knowledge is only useful for verification purposes, the program's runtime behaviour must not be affected by snapshots [Filliâtre et al. (2016)].

Since CREUSOT allows developers to include snapshots' results as part of the code, snapshots' values are converted into unit values during compilation. To ensure that erased values are not used by real code, snapshots are encapsulated in a zero-sized type monad, called `Snapshot<T>` where `T` is the type of the value being snapshoted.

The following example illustrates how snapshots can be used to track of memory at any given point:

```

let mut v:      Vec<i32> = vec![1, 2]; // Physical view:      Logical view:
let s: Snapshot<Vec<i32>> = snapshot!(v); // v → [1, 2]      v ↦ [1, 2]
v[0] = 3;      // v → [3, 2], s → ()    v ↦ [3, 2], s ↦ [1, 2]
assert!(v[0] == 3);
proof_assert!(s[0] == 1);

```

Figure 3: Example involving the snapshot feature, showing physical view (\rightarrow) and logical view (\mapsto)

This example defines a vector v , takes a snapshot of it, modifies the vector, and finally asserts that both the resulting vector v and the snapshot s (before modification of the vector) have the intended values.

The ownership of v is not transferred to the snapshot, because snapshots are erased ($s \rightarrow ()$). In the logical view, the vector at the current program point ($v \mapsto [1, 2]$) is duplicated in the logic ($s \mapsto [1, 2]$). Therefore, the vector v can still be mutated, modifying both the physical and logical view ($v \rightarrow [3, 2]$ and $v \mapsto [3, 2]$).

Assertions can now be successfully satisfied in both the executable code, using `assert!`, and the logical code, using `proof_assert!` which is a logical assertion that lives within the `Snapshot<T>` monad allowing the contents of the snapshot s to be read.

2.3. Unsound interactions

Without any restriction, the interactions between prophecy-based translation from RUSTHORN and snapshots can lead to unsoundness. As shown by [Xavier et al. \(To be published\)](#), the following unsound example must be rejected, but was accepted by CREUSOT:

```

let mut s = snapshot!(false); // Logical view:
let bor_s1 = &mut s; // s ↦ ⊥
// s ↦ α, bor_s1 ↦ (⊥, α)
// * α = ⊥, by resolving bor_s1 *
let bor_s2 = &mut s; // s ↦ β, bor_s1 ↦ (⊥, α), bor_s2 ↦ (⊥, β)
let unsound = snapshot!(bor_s1 == bor_s2); // ..., unsound ↦ ((⊥, α) = (⊥, β))
*bor_s2 = unsound; // s ↦ β, bor_s1 ↦ (⊥, α), bor_s2 ↦ (¬β, β)
// * ¬β = β, by resolving bor_s2 *
proof_assert!(false);

```

Figure 4: Example of unsoundness between snapshots and mutable borrows

This example takes a snapshot s of the value `false` and creates a mutable borrow `bor_s1` of s , generating a new prophecy α ($bor_s1 \mapsto (\perp, \alpha)$) which is resolved immediately ($\alpha = \perp$). Another mutable borrow `bor_s2` of s is created, generating a new prophecy β ($bor_s2 \mapsto (\perp, \beta)$).

A new snapshot `unsound` is taken that compares `bor_s1` and `bor_s2` (`unsound \mapsto ((\perp, \alpha) = (\perp, \beta))`), which is equal to `unsound \mapsto \neg\beta` after simplifications), and places it back into `bor_s2` (here, `bor_s2 \mapsto (\neg\beta, \beta)`).

At this point, the borrow `bor_s2` has the negation of the final value as its current value. Therefore, when *resolved*, the equality assertion (here, $\beta = \neg\beta$) is equivalent to falsity, resulting in an unsoundness hole.

The key problem is a causality loop, whereby the final value of a prophecy depends on its own current value. In this example, the logical equality of the borrows compares the pair of current and final values of their logical models. When the result of the comparison (here, `unsound`) is put back to the borrower (here, `bor_s2`), the prophecy now depends on itself, which leads to the unsoundness.

In [Xavier et al. \(To be published\)](#), a new representation of mutable borrows prevents the unsoundness by making borrows *non-extensional* by adding a new *identity* field that is unique to each borrow, making it logically distinct from other existing borrows: Two borrows are no longer equal because one of their components is different.

In the [Figure 4](#), the identities of each borrower differ, meaning the comparison is always \perp (instead of $\neg\beta$) regardless of the prophecy of `bor_s2`. On the other hand and as a global invariant, if two borrowers share the same identity, they will have the same final value.

However, no formal proof has yet been completed. One question that arises is whether the proposed modification would be sufficient and even sound.

3. The RUSTHORNBELT foundational tool

This section will draw an overview of the underlying initial model of CREUSOT, explained in [Section 2.1](#).

The context leading to the development of a foundational RUST model will be explained ([Section 3.1](#)), followed by the definition of a type system featuring *functional correctness* ([Section 3.2](#)), and a tentative to integrate snapshot in this type system ([Section 3.3](#)).

3.1. RUSTHORNBELT’s underlying model: RUSTBELT

RUST’s type system ensures memory safety¹ through the RUST’s fundamental principle. However, some programs do not respect this fundamental principle through the type system, but maintain memory safety by relying on external primitives, such as synchronisation mechanisms like locks.

These mechanisms safely allow the modification of an internal state through an aliased reference. This pattern, called *interior mutability*, requires `unsafe` blocks which exploit the “unsafe fragment” of RUST. This breaks the fundamental principle and is considered “unsafe” since a faulty implementation could lead to memory corruption.

A type can still be considered as safe, even if it uses interior mutability, as long as the exposed user interface is designed in *such a way* that it prevents the user from performing memory corruption.

The safety of such an exposed user interface is only claimed by the authors, as RUST’s type system cannot guarantee that the fundamental principle still holds. This has led to soundness problems, even within RUST’s standard library such as a `datarace` in `thread::scope` [[Miri \(2022\)](#)].

RUSTBELT [[Jung et al. \(2017\)](#)] has tackled this issue by developing a type system alongside a semantic model for λ_{Rust} , a significant subset of the RUST language that has been formalised in the ROCQ proof assistant using the separation logic framework IRIS [[Jung et al. \(2018\)](#)].

On one hand, λ_{Rust} programs that do not use `unsafe` can be proven safe using syntactic typing rules (\vdash). On the other hand, λ_{Rust} programs that do use `unsafe` can be proven safe using semantic typing rules (\models), a process known as adequacy. A logical relation has been established to link syntactic and semantic typing rules, known as the fundamental theorem of logical relation.

On top of separation logic, a lifetime logic has been introduced to represent the ownership of an object. This can be used to define a set of lifetimes \mathbf{L} that are currently alive and a type context \mathbf{T} , as a sequence of objects \mathbf{a} of type T that are either owned (noted $\mathbf{a} : T$) or borrowed under the lifetime \mathbf{a} (noted $\mathbf{a} : \mathbf{a} T$).

¹RUST’s operational semantics is not yet formally defined, despite ongoing work such as MiniRust [[MiniRust \(2022\)](#)].

RUSTBELT was a significant step forward but mainly focuses on memory safety, which prevents a user to add functional properties to prove both memory safety and functional correctness. RUSTHORNBELT [Matsushita et al. (2022)] has improved upon RUSTBELT by incorporating RUSTHORN encoding (described in Section 2.1) to handle functional correctness. It also proves that the representation remains valid in the presence of interior mutability and, more generally, in presence of unsafe code.

3.2. Type-specification system

This subsection presents how RUST types are represented (Section 3.2.1) and an overview of the type system (Section 3.2.2), followed by typing rules for mutable borrows (Section 3.2.3). Finally, these notions are summarised in an example (Section 3.2.4).

The presented type system has been proven sound, meaning that a closed and semantically well-typed RUST program, under the precondition \top , will never encounter undefined behaviour (formalised as a “stuck state”), under any execution trace. The interested reader is invited to look at the section 3.5 (PROVING SOUNDNESS OF TYPE-SPEC RULES) of the RUSTHORNBELT paper [Matsushita et al. (2022)].

3.2.1. Value types

In order to reason about functional correctness, RUSTHORNBELT’s type system associates each RUST type with a set that contains the mathematical representation of its values. The following table shows an excerpt of RUSTHORNBELT’s types, most of which are directly linked to RUST primitive types:

RUST type τ	RUSTHORNBELT type T	Mathematical type $[T]$	Intuitive semantics
<code>bool</code>	<code>bool</code>	$b : \mathbb{B}$	Booleans with value b
<code>i*/u*</code>	<code>int</code>	$n : \mathbb{Z}$	Unbounded integers with value n
<code>(T1, T2)</code>	$T_1 \times T_2$	$(x_1, x_2) : [T_1] \times [T_2]$	Tuples with field values x_1 and x_2
<code>&'a T</code>	$\&_{\text{shr}}^{\text{'a}} T$	$x : [T]$	Shared references with value x of type $[T]$
<code>&'a mut T</code>	$\&_{\text{mut}}^{\text{'a}} T$	$(*x, \hat{x}) : [T] \times [T]$	Mutable references with <i>current value</i> $*x$ and <i>final value</i> \hat{x}
<code>std::cell::Cell<T></code>	<code>cell T</code>	$P : [T] \rightarrow \text{Prop}$	Modelisation of RUST’s <code>std::cell::Cell</code> , satisfying P

Figure 5: Excerpt of RUSTHORNBELT’s types

RUST’s primitive type `bool` and integers types, such as `i32`, are represented by the boolean type `bool` and the unbounded integer type `int`, and corresponds to mathematical booleans \mathbb{B} and mathematical integers \mathbb{Z} . As expected, RUST’s tuple `(T1, T2)` are represented by the product of each of their fields, which is the compound type $T_1 \times T_2$.

Similarly to primitive types, RUST’s shared borrows `&T` are represented by the shared reference type $\&_{\text{shr}}^{\text{'a}} T$ and hold the mathematical value x being shared, of type $[T]$.

As discussed in Section 2.1, RUSTHORNBELT’s representation of RUST’s mutable reference `&mut T` is composed of a current value, noted $*x$, and a final value, noted \hat{x} , both values are of type $[T]$.

The expressiveness of the model can be demonstrated by representing complex types such as the `std::cell::Cell<T>` type in the RUST standard library, which is represented by `cell T`. A cell’s mathematical representation is a predicate that the stored value must validate, akin to an invariant. In Section 4.3, the cell type `cell T` serves as a final example that summarises the model’s modifications.

3.2.2. Type judgement and predicate transformer

The type system has been made responsible for keeping track of the specifications required to safely execute the program P , thanks to a *composable backward predicate transformer* Φ of type $([T'] \rightarrow \text{Prop}) \rightarrow [T] \rightarrow \text{Prop}$. It calculates the precondition $([T] \rightarrow \text{Prop})$ required for the safe execution of P , given the postcondition $([T'] \rightarrow \text{Prop})$ that must hold after P has been executed, in a continuation passing style.

The type judgement of an instruction I is defined as follows: $L \mid T \vdash I \dashv r. L' \mid T' \rightsquigarrow \Phi$. Starting with a local lifetime context L and a type context T , the instruction I will returns the value r and an updated set of local lifetimes L' with a type context T' , along with the specification Φ .

As an example, here is a hypothetical type judgement for integer addition that must not exceed the value M :

$$\frac{\text{INTADDBOUNDED}}{\{\} \mid \{a : \text{int}, b : \text{int}\} \vdash a +_M b \dashv c. \{\} \mid \{c : \text{int}\} \rightsquigarrow \lambda \Phi '[a, b]. a + b \leq M \wedge \Phi [a + b]}$$

Under the context where a and b are two integers, the expression $a + b$ will consumes² the integers and returns a new integer c , without any local lifetime involved.

The specification is a function that takes a postcondition Φ and the variables required for the instruction (here, $'[a, b]$, a heterogeneous list that is destructured into a and b). Since this rule applies on the (pre)condition that there is no overflow, the assertion (here, the postcondition Φ applied to the only remaining value $c := a + b$) is provable if $a + b$ is less or equal than M .

As a side note, each typing rule only shows the elements required for the rule to be applied. Therefore, the arguments of the specification (here, $'[a, b]$) is part of a context, and the required variables (here, a and b) are extracted from it during type-checking.

3.2.3. Operations for mutable borrows

Building on the representation of mutable borrows presented in [Section 2.1](#), let's now define typing rules for creating (**MUTNEW**), writing to (**MUTWRITE**) and ending a borrow (**MUTEND**) presented below:

$$\frac{\text{MUTNEW}}{\{\} \mid \{x : T\} \vdash \text{\texttt{\textcolor{red}{\$}mut}} x \dashv b. \{ 'a \} \mid \{ b : \&_{\text{mut}}^{'a} T, x : 'a T \} \rightsquigarrow \lambda \Phi '[x]. \forall \alpha_x. \Phi [(x, \alpha_x), \alpha_x]}$$

$$\frac{\text{MUTWRITE}}{\{ 'a \} \mid \{ b : \&_{\text{mut}}^{'a} T, y : T \} \vdash *b = y \dashv \{ 'a \} \mid \{ b : \&_{\text{mut}}^{'a} T \} \rightsquigarrow \lambda \Phi '[(c, f), y]. \Phi [(y, f)]}$$

$$\frac{\text{MUTEND}}{\{ 'a \} \mid \{ b : \&_{\text{mut}}^{'a} T \} \vdash \dashv \{ 'a \} \mid \{\} \rightsquigarrow \lambda \Phi '[(c, f)]. f = c \rightarrow \Phi []}$$

$$\frac{\text{LFTEND}}{\{ 'a \} \mid \{ x : 'a T \} \vdash \dashv \{\} \mid \{ x : T \} \rightsquigarrow \lambda \Phi '[]. \Phi []}$$

Figure 6: Typing rules related to mutable borrows.

When an owned object x of type T^3 is borrowed with the instruction $\text{\texttt{\textcolor{red}{\$}mut}} x$ (**MUTNEW**), a lifetime $'a$ is created and assigned to the borrower b of type $\&_{\text{mut}}^{'a} T$, without consuming the initial object being borrowed ($x : 'a T$).

²Before being consumed, integers can be duplicated freely. In RUST, the `Copy` trait indicates this property.

³In the model, it is only possible to borrow a heap-allocated object by using RUSTHORNBELT's version of RUST's `Box<T>`.

Regarding the specification, as the final value α_x is unknown, it is necessary to quantify over all possible outcomes; hence the use of the universal quantifier. The borrower b takes the current value x and the final value α_x and the borrowed object x takes the prophesied value α_x , thereby linking the lender x and the borrower b .

Under an active lifetime $'a$, when an object y of type T is written to a borrowed object b of type $\&_{\text{mut}}^{'a} T$ with the instruction $*b = y$ (**MUTWRITE**), the object y is consumed and overwrite the borrowed value. The specification discards the current value c of the borrower and replaces it with y , without modifying the final value f .

When an owned object b of type $\&_{\text{mut}}^{'a} T$ with an active lifetime $'a$ is no longer used, the prophecy variable can be resolved at any moment, provided that the lifetime $'a$ remains active (**MUTEND**), as discussed in Section 2.1. During resolution, the object b is consumed to prevent multiple resolutions. The specification models the resolution process by equalling the current and final values of the borrow.

Thanks to the RUSTHORN's representation, the lender x is not required to be present in the context of neither **MUTWRITE** nor **MUTEND**, allowing local reasoning as desired.

When an object x of type T is *frozen* ($x : ^{'a} T$) and the lifetime $'a$ is determined no longer in use by the borrow checker, the lifetime $'a$ becomes dead and the restriction on the object is lifted (**LFTEND**). Therefore, the ownership of the object is transferred back to its original owner ($x : T$). The specification is the identity function because the resolution has already completed the necessary work.

Both **MUTEND** and **LFTEND** are ghost instructions, since they do not appear in the RUST source program. In the latter case, the end of a lifetime is determined by the borrow checker. In the former case, a concept introduced in Xavier et al. (n.d., §4), is responsible for locating the right resolution point in concrete RUST programs. However, the exact mechanism will not be explained here.

One can notice that even if the borrow checker gives incorrect results, the typing rules remains sound. Indeed, **LFTEND** might be invoked either too late, resulting in an object remaining *frozen*, or too early, resulting in the lifetime being consumed where **MUTWRITE** and **MUTEND** becomes unusable.

A last typing rule, involving *borrow subdivision* (e.g. getting $\&\text{mut } T$ out of $\&\text{mut } (T, T)$), is shown below:

$$\frac{\text{MUTUPLE SPLIT}}{\{ 'a \} \mid \{ b : \&_{\text{mut}}^{'a} (T_1 \times T_2) \} \vdash \text{let } (b_1, b_2) = b \rightarrow \{ 'a \} \mid \{ b_1 : \&_{\text{mut}}^{'a} T_1, b_2 : \&_{\text{mut}}^{'a} T_2 \} \\ \rightsquigarrow \lambda \Phi \cdot \left[\left[(b_1, b_2), (\alpha_{b_1}, \alpha_{b_2}) \right] \right] \cdot \Phi \left[(b_1, \alpha_{b_1}), (b_2, \alpha_{b_2}) \right]}$$

Figure 7: Typing rule of mutable borrow subdivision

When an owned object b of type $\&_{\text{mut}}^{'a} (T_1 \times T_2)$ (i.e., a mutable borrow of a tuple type object) is *subdivided* into two borrows thanks to a let-binding, the initial object b is consumed and provides each of its components with the same lifetime $'a$.

The specification takes the current value, (b_1, b_2) , and the final value, $(\alpha_{b_1}, \alpha_{b_2})$, of the initial product type. Each component of the current value and the final value are then dispatched to each subdivision.

3.2.4. Example: Specification of a mutable borrow

As an example to see the composability of the predicate transformer in action, let's recall the program in Figure 1 to calculate the precondition thanks to described the type system in Section 3.2.3. Specifications generated by the typing rules is shown below⁴, along with their types. Here, T_i represents the i^{th} line of the program and T_e represents the logical point at which the lifetime ends, between lines 3 and 4:

⁴The attentive reader will notice that the assignment in line 3 uses a constant literal rather than of a variable. For simplicity, the context in T_3 is given the variable $\bar{1}$, which represents the mathematical value 1.

$T_1 := \lambda \Phi' []. \Phi' [0]$	$: (\text{int} \rightarrow \text{Prop}) \rightarrow () \rightarrow \text{Prop}$	
$T_2 := \lambda \Phi' [x]. \forall(\alpha : \text{int}). \Phi' [(x, \alpha) :: \alpha]$	$: (\&_{\text{mut}}^{\text{'a}} \text{int} \times \text{int} \rightarrow \text{Prop}) \rightarrow \text{int} \rightarrow \text{Prop}$	MUTNEW
$T_3 := \lambda \Phi' [\text{bor}, \bar{1}]. \Phi' [(1, \text{bor}.2)]$	$: (\&_{\text{mut}}^{\text{'a}} \text{int} \rightarrow \text{Prop}) \rightarrow \&_{\text{mut}}^{\text{'a}} \text{int} \times \text{int} \rightarrow \text{Prop}$	MUTWRITE
$T_e := \lambda \Phi' [\text{bor}]. \text{bor}.2 = \text{bor}.1 \rightarrow \Phi' []$	$: (() \rightarrow \text{Prop}) \rightarrow \&_{\text{mut}}^{\text{'a}} \text{int} \rightarrow \text{Prop}$	MUTEND ⁵
$T_4 := \lambda \Phi' [x]. \Phi' [] \rightarrow x = 1$	$: (() \rightarrow \text{Prop}) \rightarrow \text{int} \rightarrow \text{Prop}$	proof_assert!()

Figure 8: Calculated specification of each line in the example Figure 1.

Based on these specifications, the precondition of the program in Figure 1 is computable. In proof scripts, the precondition is calculated from the bottom up by composing specifications resulting in the following steps, where $T_{i \rightarrow j}$ shows the calculated precondition from T_j up to T_i :

$$\begin{aligned}
T_{e \rightarrow 4} &:= \lambda \Phi' [\text{bor}, x]. \text{bor}.2 = \text{bor}.1 \rightarrow \Phi' [] \rightarrow x = 1 & T_{3 \rightarrow 4} &:= \lambda \Phi' [\text{bor}, x]. \text{bor}.2 = 1 \rightarrow \Phi' [] \rightarrow x = 1 \\
T_{2 \rightarrow 4} &:= \lambda \Phi' [x]. \forall(\alpha : \text{int}). \alpha = 1 \rightarrow \Phi' [] \rightarrow \alpha = 1 & T_{1 \rightarrow 4} &:= \lambda \Phi' []. \forall(\alpha : \text{int}). \alpha = 1 \rightarrow \Phi' [] \rightarrow \alpha = 1
\end{aligned}$$

Some key insights emerge during the calculation of the precondition: $T_{3 \rightarrow 4}$ no longer refers to the initial value of the borrower ($\text{bor}.1$), resulting in $T_{2 \rightarrow 4}$ no longer using the value x (here, \emptyset from the first program line). Furthermore, in $T_{2 \rightarrow 4}$, the prophecy variable α is already assigned to its final value (here, 1 from the third program line).

When the calculated precondition (here, $T_{1 \rightarrow 4}$) is applied with the postcondition of the program (here, $(\lambda _ . \top)$) under an empty context, it reduces to $\forall(\alpha : \text{int}). \alpha = 1 \rightarrow \top \rightarrow \alpha = 1$, which is equivalent to \top and easy to prove for SMT solvers.

3.3. Adding a snapshot rule naively

Following CREUSOT's syntax, the instruction `let s = snapshot!(v)` captures the value v of type T inside a `Snapshot<T>` object, which is a zero-sized type that is only useful for verification purposes. A new type is defined in the RUSTHORNBELT type system, `snap T`, which represents the captured value. The mathematical type of a snapshot is the mathematical type of the captured value ($[\text{snap } T] = [T]$).

Let's write a rule for creating snapshots with the defined type system to exhibit where the unsoundness occurs. The following unsound rule is proposed:

$$\frac{\text{SNAPSHOTTAKE}}{\{\} \mid \{v : T\} \vdash \text{let } s = \text{snapshot!}(v) \dashv s. \{\} \mid \{s : \text{snap } T, v : T\} \rightsquigarrow \lambda \Phi' [v]. \Phi' [v, v]}$$

Figure 9: The snapshot rule that captures an object v .

When an object v of any type T is captured in a snapshot using the instruction `let s = snapshot!(v)`, a snapshot s is created and the captured object is released, as creating a snapshot does not consume objects. The specification captures the object v and returns a snapshot of the value itself, along with the original object v .

However, nothing can prevent the snapshotted value v from already containing resolved borrows, which is the core soundness issue shown in Figure 4. Indeed, given the representation of mutable borrows described in Section 3.2.1, the value v captured in the snapshot could be a mutable borrow ($[\&_{\text{mut}}^{\text{'a}} T] = [T] \times [T]$), whose final value may have already been resolved.

⁵In this line, `LFTEND` is also applied as the lifetime `'a` is no longer used. However, as the specification remains unchanged, the step has been omitted in this example.

4. New type-specification system

This section outlines a high-level modification of mutable borrows to resolve the unsound snapshot rule (Section 4.1), along with the necessary changes to predicate transformers (Section 4.2). Finally, this section shows an example demonstrating how RUSTHORNBELT and CREUSOT can be used together (Section 4.3) to prove real-life applications thanks to our modifications.

4.1. Non-extensional borrows

As discussed in Section 2.1, a mutable borrow in CREUSOT is represented as a tuple of a current value and a final value. As seen in Section 3.2.1, the mathematical representation of $\&_{\text{mut}}^a T$ is the type $[T] \times [T]$. The proposed representation, as briefly discussed in Section 2.3, is a triple of a current value, a final value, and a unique identifier for each new mutable borrow, making them *non-extensional*.

This new representation gave rise to a global invariant: Given an identifier, there is only one possible final value to which the identifier corresponds. Indeed, when creating a mutable borrow b , the meaning of the final value field is to prophesied the value of this *particular* instance b when the borrow ends. It means that only the current value field and the identifier field are required in the representation.

From the type system perspective, the mathematical type of $\&_{\text{mut}}^a T$ becomes $[T] \times \mathbb{N}$, where the second compound is an identifier $i \in \mathbb{N}$. Considering the operations for mutable borrows in Section 3.2.3, particularly the **MUTEND** rule, it becomes apparent that the generated assertion generated by the resolution mechanism is no longer meaningful. Indeed, an identifier is now being made equal to a value, but it should be mapped to its final value instead.

We define a *prophecy lookup* $\pi \downarrow i$ which, given a *prophecy assignment* $\pi \in \text{ProphAsn}$ and an identifier i , provides the final value of the *prophecy variable* ξ identified by i . A prophecy assignment π , formally defined in Section 5.2, is a function that maps prophecy variables ξ to prophesied values, providing one possible *future*.

Since a borrow now contains the current value c and an identifier i , the **MUTEND** rule, given a prophecy assignment π , generates the resolution assertion $\pi \downarrow i = c$. This means that the prophecy assignment π becomes the only way to access the final value of a mutable borrow.

Because the rule **SNAPSHOTTAKE** has no access to the prophecy assignment π , as more detailed in Section 5.2, the rule is now sound. The example from Figure 4 will now correctly compare borrows by comparing their identities, which are different.

4.2. Prophetic predicate transformer

Looking at the **MUTNEW** or **MUTEND** rule specifications, the final variables α are now replaced by identifiers i . In order to correctly give the expected values to postconditions, it is necessary to resolve prophecies by calling our prophecy lookup.

Therefore, the prophecy assignment π must be given to each predicate transformers Φ , changing their types in $(\text{ProphAsn} \rightarrow [T'] \rightarrow \text{Prop}) \rightarrow \text{PropAsn} \rightarrow [T] \rightarrow \text{Prop}$. The following changes applies:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \lambda \Phi '[x]. \forall \alpha_x. \Phi [(x, \alpha_x), \alpha_x] & \text{ becomes } \lambda \Phi \pi '[x]. \forall i_x. \Phi \pi [(x, i_x), \pi \downarrow i_x] & \text{MUTNEW} \\
 \lambda \Phi '[(c, f), y]. \Phi [(y, f)] & \text{ becomes } \lambda \Phi \pi '[(c, i), y]. \Phi \pi [(y, i)] & \text{MUTWRITE} \\
 \lambda \Phi '[(c, f)]. f = c \rightarrow \Phi [] & \text{ becomes } \lambda \Phi \pi '[(c, i)]. \pi \downarrow i = c \rightarrow \Phi \pi [] & \text{MUTEND} \\
 \lambda \Phi '[(b_1, b_2), (\alpha_{b_1}, \alpha_{b_2})]. \Phi [(b_1, \alpha_{b_1}), (b_2, \alpha_{b_2})] & \text{ becomes } & \text{MUTUPLE SPLIT} \\
 \lambda \Phi \pi '[(b_1, b_2), i_b]. \forall i_{b_1}, i_{b_2}. \pi \downarrow i_b = (\pi \downarrow i_{b_1}, \pi \downarrow i_{b_2}) & \rightarrow \Phi \pi [(b_1, i_{b_1}), (b_2, i_{b_2})] &
 \end{aligned}$$

The changes performed are (1) the prophecy assignment π is now received and given back, (2) prophecy variables α are now identifiers i and (3) rules that require prophesied values use the prophecy lookup.

An interesting case is the new specification of `MUTUPLE_SPLIT`, which receives an identifier i_b from the mutable borrow and must provide an identifier for each subdivision. Therefore, the rule must generate as many identifiers as there are subdivisions (here, i_{b_1} and i_{b_2}), and generate an assertion stating that the resolution must to be equal (here, the tuple value $(\pi \downarrow i_b)$ being equal to its fields $(\pi \downarrow i_{b_1}, \pi \downarrow i_{b_2})$).

As a side note, the following precondition $T_{1 \rightarrow 4}$, from the example shown in [Section 3.2.4](#), is now obtained: $\forall(i : \mathbb{N}). i \downarrow \pi = 1 \rightarrow \Phi [] \rightarrow i \downarrow \pi = 1$, which is still equivalent to \top .

As conjectured by [Xavier et al. \(To be published\)](#), specifications are prophetic as they can use the prophecy lookup thanks to the prophecy assignment π . However, snapshots, which must not be prophetic, cannot use the prophecy lookup as they do not have access to the prophecy assignment π .

4.3. An example featuring CREUSOT

The following example demonstrates how CREUSOT can use snapshots to verify invariants, while employing axiomatised rules when dealing with `unsafe` code. Indeed, CREUSOT does not yet support interior mutability, the RUSTHORNBELT modelisation is used to write an axiomatisation of `std::cell::Cell`.

The same example has also been developed and proved in RUSTHORNBELT:

```
pub struct InvCell<T> {
    inner: std::cell::Cell<T>,
    mapping: Snapshot<Mapping<T, bool>>,
}

#[trusted]
impl InvCell<T> {
    #[requires(m[x])]
    #[ensures(result.mapping == m)]
    pub fn new(x: T, m: Snapshot<Mapping<T, bool>>) -> Self { ... }

    #[ensures(self.mapping[result])]
    pub fn get(&self) -> T where T: Copy { ... }

    #[requires(self.mapping[v])]
    pub fn set(&self, v: T) { ... }
}

pub fn cell_repeat(i: i32) {
    let s = snapshot!(|z: i32| exists<k: Int> z@ == k * i@);
    let c = InvCell::new(i, s);

    while random::<bool>() { c.set(c.get() + i); }
}
```

Figure 10: An example, in CREUSOT, verifying that a `std::cell::Cell` is correctly incrementing a value.

The axiomatised structure `InvCell` is composed of the cell itself and a mapping function, which is a predicate over value of type `T` (similar to `cell T`), as well as axiomatised `new`, `get` and `set` functions.

The function `cell_repeat`, proved by both CREUSOT and RUSTHORNBELT, always contains a cell with a multiplier of the variable `i` given as argument. However, although manual translation and proofs was required in RUSTHORNBELT, the verification in CREUSOT was significantly easier and proved within seconds.

5. Semantic model

This section describes the semantic model used to prove the validity of the modified type system.

For simplicity, the presented predicates and rules omit technical reasons related to step-indexing. The interested reader is invited to look at the section 3.5 (A TECHNICAL PROBLEM INVOLVING STEP-INDEXING) of the RUSTHORNBELT paper [Matsushita et al. (2022)].

5.1. Meaning of types

In the semantic model, every RUST type T is associated to the following tuple⁶, describing its behaviour:

$$\{ \llbracket T \rrbracket.\text{size} \in \mathbb{N}, \quad \llbracket T \rrbracket.\text{own} \in [T] \times [\text{Byte}] \rightarrow \text{iProp}, \quad \llbracket T \rrbracket.\text{shr} \in [T] \times \text{Lft} \times \text{Loc} \rightarrow \text{iProp} \}$$

The first predicate, $\llbracket T \rrbracket.\text{size}$, defines the size, in bytes, required for T to be stored in memory. As an example, $\llbracket \text{int} \rrbracket.\text{size} = 1$ for unbounded integers, and $\llbracket T_1 \times T_2 \rrbracket.\text{size} = \llbracket T_1 \rrbracket.\text{size} + \llbracket T_2 \rrbracket.\text{size}$ for product types.

The second predicate, the *owned predicate* $\llbracket T \rrbracket.\text{own}$, defines the behaviour of a type T when being owned. This predicate is parameterised by the mathematical meaning of type T , followed by a list of bytes, of size $\llbracket T \rrbracket.\text{size}$, required to contain the value. As an example, there are $\llbracket T \rrbracket.\text{own}$ predicates for some types T :

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \text{int} \rrbracket.\text{own}(x, \vec{v}) &:= \ulcorner \vec{v} = [x] \urcorner \\ \llbracket T_1 \times T_2 \rrbracket.\text{own}(x, \vec{v}) &:= \exists \vec{v}_1, \vec{x}_2. \ulcorner \vec{v} = \vec{v}_1 ++ \vec{v}_2 \urcorner * \llbracket T_1 \rrbracket.\text{own}(x.1, \vec{v}_1) * \llbracket T_2 \rrbracket.\text{own}(x.2, \vec{v}_2) \\ \llbracket \text{cell } T \rrbracket.\text{own}(P, \vec{v}) &:= \exists x. P \ x * \llbracket T \rrbracket.\text{own}(x, \vec{v}) \end{aligned}$$

In this interpretation, the integer type, `int`, is simply an unbounded integer x . Similarly, the product type, $T_1 \times T_2$, is the conjunction of each of its fields.

The last definition might be surprising at first. According to RUSTHORNBELT's types in Figure 5, the mathematical representation of the cell type, $\llbracket \text{cell } T \rrbracket = [T] \rightarrow \text{Prop}$, is a predicate P that the stored value must validate. Hence, the $\llbracket \text{cell } T \rrbracket.\text{own}$ predicate is parametrised by the predicate P of type $([T] \rightarrow \text{Prop})$, which acts as an invariant on the stored value x .

The last predicate, the *shared predicate* $\llbracket T \rrbracket.\text{shr}$, defines the behaviour of a type T when being shared, at a particular lifetime. In other words, it describes what it mean to have a shared reference to this type. This predicate cannot be inferred from $\llbracket T \rrbracket.\text{own}$ as some types have complex behaviour, such as interior mutability. Internally, $\llbracket T \rrbracket.\text{shr}$ is used in the definition of $\llbracket \&_{\text{shr}}^{\kappa} T \rrbracket.\text{own}(x, \vec{v}) := \exists \ell. \vec{v} = [\ell] * \llbracket T \rrbracket.\text{shr}(x, \kappa, \ell)$.

The parameters of $\&_{\text{shr}}^{\kappa} T$ are the lifetime κ of the shared reference, the mathematical representation x of type T and the location ℓ where the shared reference points to. Followed by the previous example, there are $\llbracket T \rrbracket.\text{shr}$ predicates for some types T :

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \text{int} \rrbracket.\text{shr}(\kappa, x, \ell) &:= \exists \vec{v}. \&_{\text{frac}}^{\kappa}(\lambda q. \ell \mapsto^q \vec{v}) * \llbracket \text{int} \rrbracket.\text{own}(x, \vec{v}) \\ \llbracket T_1 \times T_2 \rrbracket.\text{shr}(\kappa, x, \ell) &:= \llbracket T_1 \rrbracket.\text{shr}(\kappa, x.1, \ell) * \llbracket T_2 \rrbracket.\text{shr}(\kappa, x.2, \ell + \llbracket T_1 \rrbracket.\text{size}) \\ \llbracket \text{cell } T \rrbracket.\text{shr}(\kappa, P, \ell) &:= \&_{\text{na}}^{\kappa/\iota}(\exists x, \vec{v}. \ell \mapsto \vec{v} * P \ x * \llbracket T \rrbracket.\text{own}(x, \vec{v})) \end{aligned}$$

When an integer is shared, the current value \vec{v} the reference points to is behind a *fractured borrow* $\&_{\text{frac}}^{\kappa} R$ of the ownership of the memory cell ℓ . Fractured borrows represent temporary ownership of some resource R , limited by a given lifetime κ , where only some fraction q of the content is given, allowing reads but not writes. Similarly to the owned predicate, the sharing predicate for tuples is the separating conjunction of the sharing predicates of its components.

⁶In practice, this tuple is more complex, capturing details about memory layout and the conditions that need to be satisfied.

When a cell is shared, the current value of the cell is wrapped in a *non-atomic borrow* $\&_{\text{na}}^{\kappa/t} I$, representing temporary ownership of an invariant I within a thread t , limited by a given κ . In this interpretation, when accessing the invariant I results in the same behaviour as the cell's owned predicate. This means that a shared cell can be accessed mutably, effectively representing interior mutability.

As this document only provides intuitive ideas for its own examples, it does not cover further examples using RUSTBELT's lifetime logic or the properties implied by these predicates. The interested reader is invited to look at the section 4 (A SEMANTIC MODEL OF λ_{Rust} TYPES IN IRIS) of the RUSTBELT paper [Jung et al. (2017)].

5.2. Parametric prophecies

RUSTHORN's encoding of mutable borrows ($\&_{\text{mut}}^a T$) implies that the semantic meaning of mutable borrows must consider all possible outcomes of the prophecy, similarly to the rule **MUTNEW**.

To that end, RUSTHORNBELT introduced the concept of *parametric prophecies* inside the IRIS framework, a prophecy framework which is presented briefly here. The interested reader is invited to look at the section 3.2 (OUR KEY INNOVATION: PARAMETRIC PROPHECIES) of the RUSTHORNBELT paper [Matsushita et al. (2022)].

A *prophecy variable* $\xi \in \mathbb{N}$ is defined as a unique identifier. To consider all possible outcomes of a prophecy variable ξ , the prophecy framework introduced a *prophecy assignment* $\pi \in \text{ProphAsn}$ which is giving one possible *future*, defined as a function that maps from prophecy variables (ξ) to prophesied values ($\pi \xi : T$).

A prophecy lookup $\pi \downarrow i$ is therefore defined as a function that maps an identifier i to its prophesied value given a prophecy assignment π ($\pi \downarrow i := \pi i$). Here, the identifier i acts like the prophecy variable ξ , as both identifiers match and therefore correspond to the same prophecy.

The prophecy assignment π is embedded in a reader monad $\nu\pi \in \text{Proph } T := \text{ProphAsn} \rightarrow T$. This monad takes a prophecy assignment π and gives a prophesied value of type T . Thanks to this monad, a prophecy's value can only be read if the prophecy assignment π is available. Therefore, if the prophecy's value must be picked (*i.e.* an existential quantifier), the picked value remains parametric in the prophetic assignment π , which is mandatory for some semantic rules, like mutable borrows as demonstrated in Section 5.3.

RUSTHORNBELT also introduced the *prophecy observation* construct $\langle \lambda\pi. \nu\pi \pi \rangle$, which ensures that any future π that has held for any resolution so far, the proposition $\nu\pi$ applied to π holds. The following rules for reasoning about observations are straightforward:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \text{PROPHTRUE} & \text{PROPHIMPL} & \text{PROPHMERGE} \\ \frac{\forall\pi. \nu\pi \pi}{\langle \lambda\pi. \nu\pi \pi \rangle} & \frac{\forall\pi. \nu\pi \pi \rightarrow \nu\pi' \pi}{\langle \lambda\pi. \nu\pi \pi \rangle \vdash \langle \lambda\pi. \nu\pi' \pi \rangle} & \frac{\langle \lambda\pi. \nu\pi \pi \rangle * \langle \lambda\pi. \nu\pi' \pi \rangle}{\langle \lambda\pi. \nu\pi \pi \wedge \nu\pi' \pi \rangle} \end{array}$$

The following rules are for the resolution mechanism of a prophecy $\xi^7, ^8$:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \text{PROPHINTRO} & \text{PROPHRESOLVE} \\ \frac{}{\text{True} \Rightarrow \exists\xi. [\xi]} & \frac{}{[\xi] \Rightarrow \langle \lambda\pi. \pi \xi = \nu\pi \pi \rangle} \end{array}$$

For each unique identifier ξ , a *prophecy token* $[\xi]$ is automatically created and signifies that ξ has not yet been resolved (**PROPHINTRO**). When resolving, it suffices to give back the prophecy token $[\xi]$, preventing multiple resolutions. It can then be *observed* that the mapping of the prophecy assignment π of this specific ξ gives the same value as the predicted future of the reader monad $\nu\pi$ of the same prophecy assignment π (**PROPHRESOLVE**).

⁷The *view-shift* $P \Rightarrow Q$ means that a resource of P turns into a resource of Q by updating the internal state.

⁸A simplified version of **PROPHRESOLVE** is shown here. A generalisation handle prophecies that depend on other prophecies, required notably for *borrow subdivision*.

As shown below, RUSTHORNBELT's model differs from our model, presented in Section 5.1, in that it does not define the mathematical meaning of a type T in owned and shared predicates using a reader monad:

$$\{ \llbracket T \rrbracket . \text{size} \in \mathbb{N}, \quad \llbracket T \rrbracket . \text{own} \in \mathbf{Proph} [T] \times [\text{Byte}] \rightarrow \text{iProp}, \quad \llbracket T \rrbracket . \text{shr} \in \mathbf{Proph} [T] \times \text{Lft} \times \text{Loc} \rightarrow \text{iProp} \}$$

This change is a major simplification that avoids the need to check prophetic dependencies in many rules, deal with complex projections with regarding tuples, or make observational equalities on invariants as these must remain true for any possible future.

In RUSTHORNBELT's model, the reader monad $v\pi$ was used to semantically model mutable borrows, particularly for the final values being of type T . As our model changed to have an identifier instead, this requirement was lifted to prophetic predicate transformers.

5.3. Behaviour of mutable borrows

So far, the behaviour of mutable borrows has not yet been defined. From RUSTBELT's lifetime logic, the definition of the borrow proposition $\&^{\kappa}P$ defines temporary ownership of the IRIS proposition P , but only during the lifetime κ . The three following rules accompany this definition⁹:

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{LFTLINTRO} \\ \hline \text{True} \Rightarrow \exists \kappa. [\kappa] * ([\kappa] \Rightarrow * [\dagger\kappa]) \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{LFTLBOR} \\ \hline P \Rightarrow * \&^{\kappa}P * ([\dagger\kappa] \Rightarrow * P) \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{LFTLBORACC} \\ \hline \&^{\kappa}P * [\kappa] \Rightarrow * P * (P \Rightarrow * \&^{\kappa}P * [\kappa]) \end{array}$$

For each unique lifetime κ , a *lifetime token* $[\kappa]$ is automatically created and signifies that the lifetime κ is still alive (**LFTLINTRO**), in a similar way as prophecy tokens $[\xi]$. When a lifetime κ is no longer active, the lifetime token $[\kappa]$ is transformed into a *dead lifetime token* $[\dagger\kappa]$ ($[\kappa] \Rightarrow * [\dagger\kappa]$).

To create a borrow proposition $\&^{\kappa}P$, it is sufficient to provide a proposition P , which will be returned when the lifetime κ is no longer active, thanks to the dead lifetime token $[\dagger\kappa]$ (**LFTLBOR**). To access the proposition P when the lifetime κ is active, both the borrowed proposition $\&^{\kappa}P$ and a lifetime token $[\kappa]$ must be provided (**LFTLBORACC**).

When defining $\llbracket \&_{\text{mut}}^a T \rrbracket . \text{own}$, a borrow proposition is used over a predicate that keeps the value of the borrow. However, the predicate P cannot pick a specific value, which prevents the value from being modified. It is therefore necessary to quantify the value existentially and communicate between both inside and outside of the borrow proposition.

Thanks to the expressiveness of IRIS, it is possible to define a value observer $\text{VO}_{\xi}(P)$ (inside the borrow proposition) and a prophecy controller $\text{PC}_{\xi}(P)$ (outside the borrow proposition). Those definitions are a typical-IRIS linked ghost state that must agree and can be updated but only jointly.

The semantic interpretation of a mutable variable becomes straightforward:

$$\llbracket \&_{\text{mut}}^a T \rrbracket . \text{own}((c, \xi), \ell) := \text{VO}_{\xi}(\lambda_{-}. c) * \&^{\kappa}(\exists x, \vec{v}. \ell \mapsto \vec{v} * \text{PC}_{\xi}(\lambda_{-}. c) * \llbracket T \rrbracket . \text{own}(x, \vec{v}))$$

Thanks to the **PROPHRESOLVE**, the resolution of a mutable borrow can be defined as follows:

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{UNIQRRESOLVE} \\ \hline \text{VO}_{\xi}(\lambda_{-}. v) * \text{PC}_{\xi}(\lambda_{-}. v') \Rightarrow \langle \lambda \pi. \pi \xi = v \rangle * \text{PC}_{\xi}(\lambda_{-}. v) \end{array}$$

Once the value observer and the prophecy controller have agreed on the value v , the value observer is given to produce the observation that the prophecy assignment π on ξ is now the value v . The prophecy controller is then returned in order to re-establish the invariant required to close the borrow.

⁹The *view-shift wand* $P \Rightarrow * Q$ denotes a resource R satisfying the view-shift $R * P \Rightarrow Q$.

Thanks to the RUSTBELT’s semantic types and lifetime logic, as well as RUSTHORNBELT’s parametric prophecies framework, the meaning of a type judgement can be defined as follows:

$$\llbracket \mathbf{L} \mid \mathbf{T} \vdash \mathbf{I} \dashv \mathbf{r}. \mathbf{L}' \mid \mathbf{T}' \rightsquigarrow \Phi \rrbracket := \\ \forall \Psi. \left\{ \exists \bar{i}. \langle \lambda \pi. \Phi (\Psi \pi) (\bar{i} \pi) \rangle * \llbracket \mathbf{L} \rrbracket * \llbracket \mathbf{T} \rrbracket(\bar{i}) \right\} \mathbf{I} \left\{ \mathbf{r}. \exists \bar{o}. \langle \lambda \pi. (\Psi \pi) (\bar{o} \pi) \rangle * \llbracket \mathbf{L}' \rrbracket * \llbracket \mathbf{T}' \rrbracket(\bar{o}) \right\}$$

The type judgement is a Hoare triple over the instruction \mathbf{I} , over an arbitrary postcondition Ψ . It is *observed* that the values of the output objects \bar{o} should satisfy Ψ , whereas the values of the input objects \bar{i} should satisfy the precondition calculated by the predicate transformer Φ , given the same Ψ .

The lifetime context’s semantics $\llbracket \mathbf{L} \rrbracket$ is the iterated separating conjunction of lifetime tokens $[\kappa]$ along with the proposition to end each lifetime in \mathbf{L} ($[\kappa] \Rightarrow * [\dagger \kappa]$).

Similarly, the type context’s semantics $\llbracket \mathbf{T} \rrbracket(\bar{c})$ is the iterated separating conjunction of the semantics of each object in the context \bar{c} . The semantics for an owned object $\mathbf{a} : T$ is the owned predicate $\llbracket T \rrbracket.\text{own}(a, \mathbf{a})$, whereas the semantics for a borrowed object $\mathbf{a} : {}^a T$ is the same owning predicate, but it is only accessible once a dead token $[\dagger \kappa]$ is provided.

6. Related work

This section describes RUST verification tools using a prophetic encoding of borrows.

RUSTHORN [Matsushita et al. (2021)] first introduced the concept of a prophetic translation of borrows by translating a core subset of RUST to constrained Horn clauses. However, it is designed for automated verification of unannotated programs and does not handle specifications, or other features for functional correctness verification.

RUSTHORNBELT [Matsushita et al. (2022)] (*which this work rely upon*) is a formalisation of the RUSTHORN approach within the ROCQ proof assistant. Although it does not handle automation, the properties of RUSTHORNBELT (*and this work*) can now be used as axioms by non-foundational tools (*as outlined in the Section 4.3 of this document*).

CREUSOT [Denis et al. (2022)] is the spiritual successor of RUSTHORN and is based on the RUSTHORNBELT model. To our knowledge, CREUSOT is the only deductive verification tool for RUST that uses a prophecy-based encoding of mutable borrows, as well as functionalities related to the challenges presented. CREUSOT targets a more complex language than λ_{RUST} , which is RUST’s MIR intermediate representation. Therefore, the resolution mechanism differs significantly: RUSTHORNBELT is limited to perform resolution on variables, whereas specific analysis must be performed in RUST’s MIR to handle the notion of *places*.

REFINEDRUST [Gäher et al. (2024)] is, like our work, a tool embedded into ROCQ using the IRIS separation logic. REFINEDRUST is inspired by RUSTHORN’s prophetic encoding, in which a borrow is interpreted as a pair of its current value and a *borrow name*, reminiscent of a prophecy variable. However, when a borrow is resolved, a separation logic assertion is produced relating the borrow name to its final value. Like CREUSOT, REFINEDRUST is an automated tool targeting RUST’s MIR, but is adapted for verifying *unsafe* RUST code and does not yet support ghost code.

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